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Fatty Acids from Anacardiaceae Seed Oils

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SEEDS from *Rhus wallichii* and *Choerospondias axillaris* belonging to the family Anacardiaceae have been analysed for the oil contents, and their fatty acid composition was determined using tlc-glc techniques.

presence of conjugated double bonds was ruled out with the help of uv-analysis. The picric acid tlc test^a for epoxy function and Halphen test^b for cyclopropenoid moiety in both the oils were found to be negative. Both the oils contained the common fatty acids in varying proportions (Table 1). In the oil from *C. axillaris*, the percentage of linoleic acid, an essential fatty acid, was as high as ~61% which is of great importance from the point of view of nutrition. However, low oil content (8%) may affect potential utility of this species. *R. wallichii* was found to contain the amount of palmitic acid (~70%), higher than ever reported in any other species. This species with moderate oil content (~13%) may be profitably used for the manufacture of detergents, surfactants, lubricants and in confectionary products.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SEEDS AND OILS

Source	Oil content %	I.V.	S.V.	Component acids (wt. %) by glc						
				12:0	14:0	16:0	18:0	18:1	18:2	18:3
<i>C. axillaris</i>	8.1	139.5	195.5	—	—	11.0	0.6	27.1	60.7	0.5
<i>R. wallichii</i>	12.7	50.9	207.6	0.5	0.8	69.8	0.8	6.8	20.6	0.8

I.V. = Iodine value, S.V. = saponification value.

Experimental

The air-dried seeds were powdered and extracted thoroughly with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The solvents were removed under vacuum at 40° to obtain the oil. The analytical values of oil and seeds were determined according to the procedures recommended by the AOCS¹. Ir and uv spectra of oils were recorded with the help of a Perkin-Elmer 621 and a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer, respectively. A Perkin-Elmer 154 analytical gas chromatograph equipped with a thermal detector using DEGS column (220°) with nitrogen as a carrier gas was used for fatty acid analysis.

The ir spectra of the oils had absorption peaks at 3000s and 1650w cm⁻¹, indicating ordinary unsaturation. There was no peak in the regions of trans-unsaturation and/or unusual functions. The

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Essential Oil of Indian *Cryptomeria japonica*

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CRYPTOMERIA *japonica*, an exotic from Japan, is an evergreen tree cultivated as plantation in the northern part of Bengal. In contrast to the